

***IN SITU* TENSILE FIBRE FAILURE ANALYSIS BY SYNCHROTRON RADIATION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY**

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Keywords: *Computed Tomography, Damage Accumulation, Fibre Break Clustering*

1. General Introduction

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) offer superior properties for structural applications, including high specific stiffness and strength, good fatigue behaviour, and excellent corrosion resistance [1]. However there are also reliability issues with CFRPs which revolve around the nature and progression of damage within them [2].

Fibre failure is the critical damage mechanism for composites loaded in tension, as the strength of the axially loaded unidirectional composite is dominated by fibre strength. The progression from a single fibre break, to multiple breaks, and ultimately final failure is yet to be fully understood and quantified, particularly within commercially produced composites.

The difficulty in predicting failure arises from the multiple interacting failure mechanisms occurring in three dimensions [3]. The changes in damage state during failure, and how these relate to changes in the material response, need to be accurately represented by failure models [4]. Currently the experimental evidence to corroborate the assumptions underpinning the models is limited, meaning they remain unvalidated. We aim to link experimental results to simulation tools, thus the results will provide physical validation for the selection and calibration of fibre break models.

High resolution synchrotron radiation computed tomography (SRCT) enables a physical insight into composite failure processes, allowing fibre breaks to be identified and quantified in three dimensions. The aim of the paper is then to use SRCT to quantify the microstructure, micromechanical features, and failure mechanisms of CFRPs under tensile loading in three dimensions. The coupling of SRCT and *in-situ* loading permits analysis of damage progression

in bulk specimens, which are representative of commercially available systems.

The focus of the present work is to show how fibre break accumulation under tensile load, varies between commercially representative CFRP systems. The variation in break density and the rate of break accumulation as a function of fibre stress is analysed. Particular attention is focused on the formation of clusters of broken fibres, as the development of a critical number of closely-spaced fibre breaks is often assumed to be the strength-defining failure event [5, 6]. An analysis of the differing cluster sizes, shapes and percentages, with respect to the material systems has been undertaken. The results give a unique physical insight into the composite failure process, enabling the variation in fibre break and clustering parameters to be quantified.

2. Methodology

Six material systems were investigated, and the results compared to those from a similar system (IMC/M1) [7]. The exact constituents and properties are proprietary, so the values have been normalised, to provide an indication of the relative values across the fibres, matrices and composite, as shown in Table 1.

The specimens were 4mm wide double-notched coupons, which were cut using water-jet cutting. Previous research has shown that no significant damage is induced by the cutting process [8]. Aluminium tabs were bonded to the coupon ends to enable loading, and reduce the stress concentrations at the loading ends. Ten specimens from each plate were tensile tested to determine the nominal failure

load of each system. The specimens were incrementally loaded *in situ* up to eight percentages of nominal failure load. A description of the rig, which is shown in figure 1, and the testing methodology is provided in Wright *et al* [9].

All coupons except IMB/T and IMB/UT were taken to eight increments of nominal failure load (10,70,80,90,95,98,100,105%) with scans at each step. Due to time constraints IMB/T and IMB/UT could only be taken to five increments (10, 75, 93, 98, 100%). As only nominal failure loads are known, and because of the stochastic nature of fibres, some specimens failed at lower load steps resulting in fewer scans for analysis; this was particularly true for IMD/M1 and IMB/T where the highest load steps achieved were 87% and 82% respectively.

Tomographic x-ray scans were undertaken on the TOMCAT beamline at the Swiss Light Source (SLS), Paul Scherrer Institut, Villigen, Switzerland. A resolution of 0.6 μm was used, with a detector size of 2560 x 2160 pixels. A propagation distance of 30mm allowed a degree of near-field Fresnel edge enhancement, which makes it easier to identify individual fibre breaks.

Reconstruction was undertaken using in-house software at the SLS, and break analysis was performed using VG-Studio™. Breaks were identified through visual inspection of the data files, inspecting at least two orthogonal planes to ensure accuracy, and extracted from the bulk composite. An example break in two orthogonal views is shown in figure 2. The volumes analysed ranged between approximately 0.15 and 0.3mm³, which represents 8,000 – 14,000 fibres in the 0° plies. An example of the analysed volume is shown in figure 2, in which delaminations, matrix cracks and fibre breaks can all clearly be seen.

3. Analysis

3.1 Calculation of Fibre Stress

The variations in specimen cross-section and fibre volume fraction both need to be accounted for when calculating the stress in the 0° ply fibres. Due to delaminations, the 0° and 90° plies become decoupled; hence we assume that the 90° plies carry

no load. The fibre stress was calculated using the rule of mixtures for a nominal 0° ply area, as defined in figure 3. Microscopy was used to accurately determine the fibre diameters, as SRCT images give good fibre counts, but relatively poor fibre cross-sectional area measurements due to the resolution of the images.

A plot of the fibre stress at each analysed load step is shown in figure 5. Whilst the majority of specimens lie on a middle band, IMB/T and IMB/UT lie above it, whilst IMD/M1 lies below. This means that fibres in IMD/M1 experience higher fibre stresses at the comparative load steps. This may be due to IMD/M1 having a noticeably low volume fraction, due to very large resin rich regions.

3.2 Fibre Break Accumulation

The fibre break density (breaks/mm³) as a function of fibre stress is shown in figure 6. IME/M2 is not included as it has no other specimen to compare to. The IMA specimens (T and UT) lie on the same line, as do the IMB specimens (T and UT); however IMC/M1 and IMD/M1 do not. This implies that the matrix, and in particular, the presence of toughening particles does little to influence break accumulation.

IMD/M1 sits below the curve, which implies it accumulates breaks at the later stages of loading. It can be seen that specimens with fibre IMA sit on the top side of the curve, i.e. more breaks occur in the early stages of loading. IMA, the strongest fibre, also accumulated breaks at lower fibre stress values, highlighting the stochastic nature of fibre strengths.

IMB/T and IMB/UT had very high break densities at their respective highest load steps of 82% and 98%. This suggests that the fibre is more susceptible to breaking; however this does not appear to have a detrimental effect on composite strength, as specimens made with IMB fibres had the highest UTS, despite containing average strength fibres.

3.3 Cluster Shapes

The occurrence of fibre break clusters indicates the role of load sharing in the accumulation of damage. In the present work a cluster is defined as two or more breaks in neighbouring fibres, separated

axially by less than the fibre's ineffective length [7]. The literature indicates that cluster formation is dependent on the stress concentration, which in turn is dependent on material properties [10, 11]. Co-planar clusters are more likely to form in fibres with a high Weibull modulus, or stronger, more elastic matrices [10, 11]. Cluster shapes will also be dependent on the fibre/matrix adhesion; a stronger interface will result in co-planar clusters [12]. As the sizing/adhesion properties are not known, we are not able to take into account the role of sizing on cluster formation.

Two different cluster patterns have been identified and are shown in figure 4, where (a) shows a co-planar cluster and (b) shows a diffuse cluster. Co-planar breaks are defined as collections of breaks with an axial separation of less than a couple of microns.

Scott found pre-preg, autoclave cured IMC/M1 specimens had co-planar clusters of up to 14 breaks [13]. All current specimens contained co-planar breaks, except for IMB/UT where the majority (87%) of clusters were diffuse. The occurrence of co-planar and diffuse clusters in different systems with the same manufacturing process indicates that cluster patterns are not solely dependent on the manufacturing route. The patterns suggest differences in load transfer mechanisms: co-planar clustering implies little-to-no debonding and hence a strong interface.

3.4 Cluster Percentage

The clusters were analysed using the clustering code described in [7]. The cluster percentage (CP) has then been calculated as:

$$CP = \frac{\text{Number of breaks in clusters}}{\text{Total number of breaks}} \times 100$$

Figure 7 shows the cluster percentage in the flat plate specimens. Here the total number of breaks in an i-plet is accounted for, therefore one 2-plet contributes two breaks to the overall break count. This allows the contribution of i-plets to the total number of breaks to be accounted for; otherwise a large percentage of breaks are not considered.

The results indicated that IMC/M1 and IME/M2, the fibres with the highest known Weibull values, were most susceptible to clustering, with a cluster percentage of up to 50%. IMA/T and IMA/UT, the fibres with the lowest Weibull values, were least susceptible with a cluster percentage up to 20% but as low as 0. The presence of toughening particles did not alter the cluster percentage. Across the current systems, the cluster size ranged from a 3-plet to a 7-plet, compared to the 14-plet found in IMC/M1 [7].

The percentage of breaks in clusters vs. the fibre break density for each of the systems has been plotted. From figure 8 it can be seen that there are three main groups of clustering data which have been grouped into similar fibre strengths. For both IMA (dashed line) and IMB (solid line), the presence of toughening particles does not make a difference to the cluster percentage. However it can be seen that the higher strength fibres, IMA, IMD (un-circled) and IMB, have lower clustering percentages than the lower strength fibres IMC and IME (dotted line).

No correlation was found between the overall cluster percentage and load, or cluster percentage and overall fibre break density. However the largest individual clusters sizes in each material system were found at the highest load levels. Overall it was found that fibres IMD and IMA were much less susceptible to clustering than the other three fibre types. IMB had both a high fibre break density and a high cluster percentage, indicating that the fibre fractured more frequently than the other fibres at a given load.

The composite with fibre IMA (the strongest fibre) had the lowest average cluster percentage, however the composite failure stress does not reflect this, as it is one of the lowest. Thus there is a need to understand the interaction between fibre/matrix constituents, and the failure mechanisms behind composites when designing structures.

3.5 Cluster tracking

In-situ loading enables the damage progression and the accumulation of clusters to be monitored and quantified. The methodology allows specific clusters to be identified in sequential data sets to

determine whether clusters grow incrementally or form within one load step. This will provide data relating to whether cluster accumulation is dynamic or quasi-static.

Initial analysis has found that most clusters, (upwards of 90%), do not grow in between load steps. This means that clusters form at a certain load, and then stay the same size, suggesting a dynamic process. Cluster growth was found in IMB/UT and IME/M2, in which 22% and 2% of clusters grew. As IMB/T only had one data point, it has so far not been possible to analyse whether clusters grow in the specimen

So far no correlations have been found between cluster growth and specimen type. Further testing is needed as the load steps may have been too large to capture the incremental growth. To account for this, further *in situ* testing at smaller load increments, or hold at load tests may be needed. Further analysis is needed to determine why only some clusters in the two systems grew. This suggests that cluster growth is not just a function of load transfer, but also the local microstructure surrounding the cluster.

4. Conclusions

SRCT has been used to analyse the effects of fibre and matrix types on fibre break accumulation and clustering. The fibre and matrix parameters have been shown to cause significant variations in the results. IMB fibres had particularly high fibre break densities, accumulating at the higher load steps. In contrast IMA fibres accumulated breaks at lower load steps, which suggested high fibre strength variability.

The relatively poor performance of composites containing IMA fibres highlights the need to quantify the effects of multiple parameters and micromechanical features, and the roles they play in damage accumulation and final failure. IMA is the strongest fibre, yet did not result in the strongest composite.

All specimens showed co-planar clusters apart from IMB/UT, which exhibited diffuse clusters. This indicates that clustering type is not solely a function of manufacturing. IMB appeared more susceptible to both fracture and clustering; whilst low Weibull moduli fibres, IMA and IMD, were less susceptible to clustering. Initial results found that clusters do not grow with load, suggesting a dynamic process.

Overall the paper highlights the need to understand in greater detail the interaction between constituents and composite failure mechanisms when designing a structure. Further analysis is needed to determine the effects of local micromechanical features, such as voids or fibre volume fraction variation. The work illustrates the power of high resolution SRCT to obtain previously unobtainable data sets for the failure mechanisms of composite materials.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge Luxfer Gas Cylinders Ltd., particularly Dr. Warren Hepples, and Hexcel and Cytec Industries for materials supply. The authors acknowledge Bernd Pinzer and staff at the TOMCAT/SLS beamline, and Dr Mavrogordato at the μ -VIS X-ray Imaging Centre, Southampton.

Tables and Figures

Fibre				Matrix		Composite
Type	UTS	Modulus	Weibull	Type	Modulus	UTS
IMC [3]	1	1	6	M1	1	0.44
IMD	1.2	1.29	4.4	M1	1	0.48
IME	1.16	1.2	5.57	M2	3.73	0.76
IMA	1.24	1.32	5.2	Toughened (T)	3.57	0.4
IMA				Untoughened (UT)		0.51
IMB	1.16	1.26	6.32	Toughened (T)		1.04
IMB				Untoughened (UT)		1.10

Table 1: Summary of the material system parameters, with normalised values

Figure 1 Schematic of the tensile loading rig [8]

Figure 2: Partial slice of IMB/UT at 98% of failure load; fibre breaks are circled, and arrows indicate a delamination and a matrix crack.

Figure 3 Definition of the sampling area used to determine the nominal fibre stress.

Figure 4: Example of (a) co-planar and (b) diffuse clusters

Figure 5 Graph of the applied load (N) and the resulting fibre stress for each specimen

Figure 6 Graph of the fibre break densities as a function of fibre stress

Figure 7 Cluster percentage for a) IMD/M1 and IMC/M1, b) IME/M2, where the % of final failure stress is indicated

Figure 7 Cluster percentage for c) IMA/T and IMA/UT, and d) IMB/T and IMB/UT, where the % of final failure stress is indicated

Figure 8 Graph showing the fibre break density vs. the percentage of breaks in clusters; the two encircling lines define fibres of similar strength.

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